

doi:10.5281/zenodo.18509546

Teacher Education And Integration Of Digital Tools In The Teaching Of Social Science Education In Higher Institution Of Learning

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ABSTRACT

Teachers are central to good education and determine to a large extent, the growth and development of a nation. Teacher education has been considered relevant for Nigeria's societal development because it serves as the foundation for quality and relevant education at all levels of the system. Teacher education in Nigerian schools are under-going changes especially across the ICT sector in the teaching of Social Sciences Education. To, achieve the best in education, teaching and learning should be activity-based learner-centered and experimental as well as ICT compliant. Traditional education system with little or no adaptation to technology is what operates in many schools. To achieve the goals of teaching and learning Social Sciences Education, teachers need to integrate more digitized learner-centered instructional approaches. Though the pedagogy of teaching Social Studies has undergone a huge change. ICTs play vital roles in facilitating teaching and learning as it has made teaching and learning of Social Sciences Education interactive and collaborative. Despite these powerful enabling tools for educational change and reforms, yet digital tools such as blogs, internet, e-mail, YouTube, mobile phones and many others are not been integrated in the Social Sciences Education classroom. This paper examines teacher education and also intends to expose the significance of integrating Digital tools into the teaching of Social Sciences Education. Thirdly, the paper would explore the Digital teaching tool such as internet, blogs, email, YouTube and others. The paper further discusses challenges and the way forward which suggested that teachers needed to be trained and updated with the knowledge of digital tools to bring innovative techniques and promote effective digital quality teaching and learning in higher institutions.

Keywords: Teacher education, Integration, Digital tools, Teaching, Social Sciences Education, Higher institution.

INTRODUCTION

Education is recognized as a process of imparting knowledge, skills and attitudes to the learners for the sake of the individual and the community to which they belong, assistance in developing one's cognitive, affective and psychomotor capacities is required (Onwiroduokit, 2020). Education is also considered as a prerequisite for quality manpower development and creation of wealth, a sure path to success in life and service to humanity. Prior to the advent of colonialism, the traditional African society had forms of teaching and learning system in which the parent or elders inculcated societal norms and values on the younger generation or to one another. Teaching takes place once an activity formal, informal lead to a change in an experience or behaviour in someone else from unknown to known.

Presently, education vis-a-vis teaching has taken a new dimension as some persons are versed with the rights and responsibilities to carry out teaching function, otherwise called a teacher. Agwu (2015) defines a professional teacher as the one possessing knowledge and methods that could bring about change and he/she must possess the willingness and ability to change human behaviour. The influence of a teacher is being felt in a sphere of the society. Educational attainment of every teacher depends to a great extent on the effectiveness of any educational system, this is a fact because no system of education can be qualitatively higher than the quality and commitment of its teachers. Consequently, such an individual must pass through some specific and specialized training through designated platforms and specialized programmes and process called Teacher Education. Ogar and Aniefioke (2012) opines that teacher education prepares educators to meet the changing demands of the profession and the needs of their communities. It includes training and or education occurring before commencement of service (pre-service) and during service (in-service). The Federal Government of Nigeria places emphasis on the teaching profession as enshrined in the National Policy on Education which stipulates amongst the goals of teacher education is to produce teachers with the intellectual and professional background adequate for their assignment and to make them adaptable to changing situations (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013). Sheminger (2018) opines that in recent decades pedagogy has undergone a profound paradigm shift moving from passive learning to active learning. The teaching and learning of English as a second language is a daunting task and has necessitated the integration of varied pedagogical principles, skills, methods and teaching aids to facilitate its effective teaching and learning encounter. The teaching and learning of the English language has advanced greatly due to the advancement of technology. Digital tools have been an integral part of education since its introduction. Digital tools are referred to as “software, programmes, applications, platforms, and resources that can be used with computers, mobile devices or other digital devices” that help people complete a task (Oikonomou, V.L. & Patsala, P, 2021). There have been numerous studies corroborating the positive effects of digital technologies in language learning (Baydask Goktas, 2016; Hockly & Dudeney, 2018; Kessler, 2018). The connection between technology and learning has become increasingly evident in recent years. The popularity of social media has given rise to a new digital culture that has transformed the way teachers and students engage with each other (Husna et. al. 2022) Perguna, et. al., (2021). The use of digital teaching tools has offered English language teachers the opportunity to jettison the archaic and parochial chalk and talk method to modern ways of teaching. Digital tools are believed to help language teachers provide timely and relevant feedback while supporting the development of all-four language skills (listening, speaking, reading and writing) (Ghanizade et. al; 2015) as well as improved self regulation and collaboration (Warni, et. al, 2018). The integration of ICTs can enhance the quality of education in several ways by increasing learner motivation and engagement by facilitating the acquisition of basic skills and by enhancing teacher training. Audu (2018) posits that the use of ICT in the classroom increases the flexibility of delivery of education so that learners can have access to knowledge at any moment and from anywhere. It is therefore important that teachers and students move beyond looking at computer, laptops, ipad, tablet and their programs as games to play but rather see them as instruments of learning. The entry of technology makes the teacher thought-provoking and more creative, therefore the English teacher would be thought less if they did not take benefit of the modern and maximum technological methods of reading, expression and communication. However, despite the huge benefits of the integration of Digital learning tools in teaching English language. Most of the teachers are not using Digital teaching tools. So it is important to show that if we use Digital tools in the English language classroom we may perhaps see a significant change in students’ attitude, motivation, participation and huge performance. In recent years, teachers have struggled to embrace digital learning tools and are not aware of how technology can affect the quality of teaching and learning (Dudency & Hockly, 2016). Majority of English language teachers do not have sufficient knowledge of digital tools and do not utilize these modern digital teaching tools. Due to a lack of technological expertise, these teachers cannot incorporate modern tools into their lessons (Merc, 2015). Mohamadkhani, Farokhi, and Farokhi (2013) are lack of knowledge about how to use technology integration in lessons, lack of resources to take off, lack enough time, lack of confidence among teachers to use integrated technology and lack of training opportunities

for teachers. As a result to the foregoing, this paper would examine teacher education, the possibility and importance of integrating modern Digital tools such as video, YouTube, internet e-mail into the teaching of English language. It would also explore challenges English language teachers face in the integration of Digital tools and explain the prospects of Digital application in the teaching of English language.

Teacher Education and Programmes in Nigeria

Teacher education as stipulated in the National Policy on Education (2013) states that no education system can rise above the quality of its teacher, teacher education shall continue to be given major emphasis in all educational planning and development. It also states that the minimum qualification for entry into teaching profession shall be the Nigerian Certificate in Education. Teacher educator equips teachers with skills, competencies and insight in the task of producing the needed manpower in the educational system.

The goal of teacher education in Nigeria as stipulated in the National Policy on Education (2013) is to produce highly motivated, conscientious, efficient classroom teachers, the encouragement of the spirit of enquiry and creativity in teachers and providing them with the intellectual and professional background that will be adequate for their assignments and also make them adaptable to changing situations. By the policy, the professional training of teachers in two-folds; pre-service and in-service trainings. To implement this, certain institutions are charged with the responsibility to produce professional training for teachers. These include; faculties/institutes of Education of universities, train teachers for secondary (high) school offering Bachelor of Education degree programmes to both senior secondary school graduates and senior secondary school teachers who already have National Certificate in Education (NCE) qualifications. They also offer Master's and Doctorate degree programmes in education. Colleges of Education; offer post-secondary NCE training Programmes, (train teachers for primary and junior secondary school). The NCE has become the minimum qualification for primary school teachers in 1998 (Teacher Registration Council, 2010). Some of the colleges also offer NCE pre-primary courses in order to produce teachers for the pre-primary level of education. The National Teachers' Institute (NTI) was established to provide refresher and upgrading courses for practicing teachers; organize workshops, seminars, and conferences as well as formulate policies and initiate programmes that would lead to improvement in the quality and content of education in the country. Also, the institute initiated training and re-training programmes for helping unqualified primary school teachers. In addition, they are also required to register with the Teachers Registration Council of Nigeria which is a body responsible for the licensing of teachers. At the fulfilment of these requirements, they are considered professional teachers.

Digital Learning

Digital learning (E-learning) was first proposed by Jay Cross in 1999 (Yoon et. Al. 2012). With the advance and development of technology tools, it appeared different explanations and terminology such as internet-based training, web-based training, online learning, network learning, distance learning. According to Doris Holzberger et al. (2013) digital learning is regarded as delivery with digital forms of media (e.g. texts or pictures) through the internet; and the provided learning contents and teaching methods were to enhance learner's learning and aimed to improve teaching effectiveness or promote personal knowledge and skills. Anttila et. al. (2012) opined that digital learning as a digital tool to acquire digital teaching materials for online or offline learning activity through wired or wireless networks. Digital learning refers to any sort of learning that makes use of and takes advantage of technology. Stephanie, Escudro, 2022. So, digital learning covers anything that includes learners using digital platforms, resources, systems, and apps. Digital learning are usually far more interactive and engaging. Digital learning becomes more of a part of the educational landscape, we can expect some substantial changes as digital learning takes hold in education. Online learning has been seen as one of the ways digital technologies and advances have affected students and trends in the classroom. Digital tools have become undoubtedly a powerful tool that would support and transform education in various ways, for example from making it easier for teachers to create course materials to providing new ways for students

to learn and collaborate with other students. Therefore, digital learning can thus change the future of education.

Use of Digital Learning Tools in Teaching Social Science Education

The use of computers and the internet form the main components of digital learning. Digital learning covers anything that includes learners use of digital platforms, resources, systems and apps. In the earlier days it was not given a positive acceptance as it was assumed that the system lacked the human element required in learning. With the use of smart phones, tablets etc. people now embraced digital learning for examples books were being replaced by electronic educational materials. Therefore, integrating Digital tools into classroom activities is the trend all over the world. The following are digital tools when integrated into the classroom would bring about effective learner-centered in teaching of Social Science Education.

Video clips

Video clips can be used to introduce a lesson because over 70 percent of communication is non-verbal, videos help students to learn and understand Social Sciences Education through body language and facial expressions. For example, teachers can show students several clips from famous movies (describing people and moods) and allow each group to brainstorm as many objects they can sport. Some are physical objects such as computers and mobile phones, while others are abstract codes or systems such as languages, counting systems or computer codes.

Internet

The internet is termed as the most useful technology of modern times. For educational purposes, the internet is used to gather information and to research. The internet is a vital tool for effective teaching as well as learning. Teachers can use it as a teaching tool by posting teaching materials for example note and videos on the school website.

YouTube

YouTube is an essential tool in the Social Science Education classroom, it is used to enhance various aspects of teaching and learning of Social Science Education in higher institution of learning. YouTube use offers real examples of interaction among students and teachers in higher institution of learning. Teachers can use internet to improve students listening, speaking, reading & writing skills.

Google classroom

Google classroom streamlines communication and assignment distribution. Teachers can share resources assign tasks and provide feedback in a centralized online environment, fostering a digital classroom experience. Here students can post their queries on the lessons taught in the classrooms and receive answers from teachers and other students.

Blog

The use of blog is becoming popular especially in education. It is a tool used to share information and generate discussions. Many teachers use blogs instead of textbooks and traditional methods to teach students and gain experience with various forms of social media.

Mobile phones

Mobile phone is another digital tool that can help conduct online classes anywhere anytime.

Twitter

Another essential digital fool for improving Social Science Education is the twitter. It is an online education tool, where teachers can use it to engage students in classroom activities to develop a better understanding of concepts.

Use of Digital Tools to Teachers

1. Digital tools enhance the initial preparation by giving good teaching and training materials, use of simulators, recording and feedback in teaching.
2. With the assistance of Digital tools, teachers can access with colleagues, schools, institutions expertise.
3. Digital tools enable interaction with students over a physical distance.
4. Didactic software and intelligent tutoring systems can reduce cost of teacher training.

5. Digital tools facilitate sharing of ideas, experience as well as collaborating on projects and exchange of material through virtual communities.

Benefits of Integrating Digital Tools in the teaching of Social Science Education

Integration of digital tools in the classroom does not, only helps teachers engage with students during lessons but students can also communicate with each other. Students can work together to solve problems, especially during online lessons and learning games. Students can share ideas, thoughts and support each other while working on collaborative activities. Digital integration in the classroom allows for one-on-one interaction with teachers. Students can upload their home work into a virtual classroom which teachers can access, view and grade completed assignment.

1. **Personalized learning opportunities:** Students can have 24/7 access to educational resources through the integration of Digital tools. It encourages students to learn at their own pace. They can also review the videos in the lesson plans if they find it necessary.
2. **Enhanced curiosity due to engaging content:** Teachers can bring out students' curiosity and boost their interest through engaging and creative educational content. Through increase curiosity, students can gain a better understanding of reading concepts.
3. **Improved teacher efficiency and productivity:** New levels of productivity can be achieved through integration of digital tools. They can also use and implement useful digital tools to expand learning opportunities for students, thereby leading to support and engagement. With the use of the right tools, teachers can improve their instructional methods and provide personalized learning.
4. **Transformed classroom experience:** With the use of digital tools classroom experiences can move from teacher-centered to that of a student-centered experience whereby students can actively take a more active role in their learning. The teacher becomes more of a guide as the students' engage with and take over the day's lessons.
5. **Ability to provide differentiated instruction:** In every classroom, there are different students with different learning abilities. With differentiated instruction, students are provided with an education that is personalized and that meets them where they are developmental.
6. **Enabling students to become global citizens:** Use of Digital tools would expose teachers and students to new, online global communities. It extends learning beyond the textbook and beyond the classroom walls: The use of digital tools promotes inclusion and the development of digital literacy skills. It promotes global awareness, which is a major element of the 21st-century education.
7. Digital tools facilitate dynamic and interactive learning experiences, thus offer students engaging activities like games, interactive exercises that make the process of learning Social Science Education more enjoyable and effective.

Challenges of Digital use by teachers in the classroom

1. The absence of clear guidelines and support systems within educational institutions may discourage teachers from exploring and adopting digital tools in their Social Science Education teaching.
2. Challenges related to teaching conditions such as disrupted internet and noisy environments-learning to communication difficulties, reduced student engagement.
3. Lack of training and knowledge of teachers on the effective usage of digital tools.
4. Technical issues such as poor internet connectivity, inadequate hardware and software access and unstable internet connections discourages teachers from using digital tools in their classrooms.
5. Difficulties in maintaining student engagement and motivation in online classes and limited opportunities for interaction and collaboration.
6. Deficient teaching materials and inadequate digital teaching skills when attempting to integrate digital learning tools.
7. Scarcity of devices available in schools.

Integration of digital tools into Social Science Education Teaching

The integration of Digital tools into Social Science Education teaching is applauded with transformative changes influencing both teachers and learners in several ways. The impact of these tools is evident across various aspects of Social Science Education acquisition and education with the use of interactive and gamified methods, digital tools enhance learning, making it more engaging for students, features like quizzes, games and multimedia content capture students' attention, thus motivating them to be actively engaged in lessons. According to Albugami and Ahmed (2016) the adoption of technology is a powerful way to contribute to changes in education. Digital tools allows for the customization of learning experiences. Teachers can tailor content to individual student needs, adapting lessons to different learning styles, paces and proficiency levels. This personalization fosters a more inclusive and effective learning environment. This accessibility makes the learning experience rich by providing students with exposure to diverse accents, cultural contexts, and real-life usage.

Digital tools enable instant feedback; thus, students can receive guidance on their performances in real time. Digital tools cater for various skills, including listening speaking, reading and writing from interactive reading platforms to language exchange apps, digital tools offer, a holistic approach to learning, addressing multiple facets of language acquisition. This efficiency allows teachers to focus more on the instructional aspects of teaching. Integrating digital tools prepares students for the demands of the digital age. Therefore, teachers are expected to be trained and apply the use of technology in their classrooms teaching as it provides assistance and guidance for teachers to follow and opportunity to use different methods to enhance teaching and learning (Ageel & Woollard, 2012).

Way forward

1. There's a gap between knowledge and usage of digital tools, therefore there is the need for teacher education programmes to improve awareness of pedagogical technological methods and provide effective training and support to address challenges faced by Social Science Education teachers.
2. Differentiated training curricula which addresses diverse specific needs of Social Science Education teachers should be developed, ensuring that teachers are equipped with necessary digital skills and knowledge.
3. There should be adequate provision of appropriate amounts of support by the schools and policy makers which would help empower teachers and promote their professional growth.
4. Students should be trained on how to apply ICT in their learning activities and daily life.
5. Provision and availability of ICT tools in all schools at all levels.

CONCLUSION

Teacher education has been considered a key component for Nigeria's societal development. It is a series of complex and complete procedure of preparing individuals whose work is imparting knowledge to other individuals with the aim of contributing to national development. Teacher education is considered to be the foundation for quality and relevance in education at all levels. In recent decades pedagogy has undergone a profound paradigm shift moving from passive learning to active learning. To achieve the goals of teaching and learning Social Science Education, teachers need to incorporate many digital tools. That would bring effective teaching with little effort as possible.

Digital tools can be used for pedagogical purposes such as facilitating the teaching and learning of the Social Science Education. Digital tools such as internet, blogs, YouTube and many others make learning more interesting, motivating and meaningful. Despite these powerful enabling digital tools, teachers are faced with challenges, their insufficient knowledge in the use of ICT such as digital tools. As technology continues to advance, the integration of digital tools will likely play an increasing crucial role in shaping the future of Social Science Education. Digital learning in teacher education can enhance quality education in Nigeria because when Digital tools are effectively integrated into Social Science Education, teachers would take the roles of adviser, content expert and coach. There is therefore the need for all Nigerian teachers to be digitally proficient because digital tools help make teaching and learning more meaningful and fun.

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